

DIGITALIZATION OF THE PROCESS OF RECORDING AND REVIEWING CRIMINAL COMPLAINTS - A REQUIREMENT OF OUR TIME

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15656742>

Abstract: The article discusses the fight against crime in the new Uzbekistan, including efforts to digitize the system for receiving and recording criminal complaints, reports, and other information, as well as the need to digitize the process of reviewing and resolving criminal data. It puts forward proposals and recommendations for improving this system through the full implementation of information technology capabilities.

Keywords: crime, complaint, recording, legality, decision digitization, unified state register, human rights.

New Uzbekistan is creating fundamentally new mechanisms for combating crime, early prevention of offenses, and maintaining public order. Indeed, in a state where peace and tranquility are guaranteed, the supremacy of the constitution and law is achieved, sustainable development is attained, and most importantly, a foundation is laid for upholding human dignity.

"In accordance with the noble principle of "For Human Dignity", ensuring a peaceful and safe life for every citizen, creating conditions for the realization of fundamental rights and freedoms, and establishing public administration in service of the people are the ultimate goals of these reforms.

"The goal of directing the activities of law enforcement agencies towards the protection of human interests, dignity, and rights in the "Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy[1] is aimed at implementing the aforementioned priority idea. Creating a unified electronic registry of crime reports is one of the main tasks for this purpose.

Moreover, at a meeting of the National Council for Combating Corruption, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev stated, "corruption is such a vicious vice that it undermines people's trust in the state, the Constitution, and laws, and becomes a serious threat to sustainable development and security"[2]. And one of the directions in the fight against corruption has been defined as the complete digitalization of the crime registration system.

According to the Head of State, the creation of a system for automatic registration of crime reports received through the "102" service, i.e., where each appeal leaves a "digital trace," has yielded results.

At the same time, some heads of district and city internal affairs bodies have been concealing crimes to improve statistics, and there have been instances of delaying registration for months.

The President, criticizing these shortcomings, put forward an initiative to provide every neighborhood's prevention center with surveillance cameras and equip each inspector with a "body camera," as well as to launch a new platform for recording offenses in order to prevent similar situations in the [future](#)[3].

Indeed, introducing a transparent mechanism for registering offenses, as well as adopting lawful and well-founded decisions on each reported appeal, is one of the important issues in combating crime. Because without impartial and objective information about crimes, it is impossible to determine effective measures to combat and prevent crimes.

Current legislation, including the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, establishes a number of norms regarding the consideration and resolution of criminal information. According to the requirements of this law, criminal statements, reports, and other information must be registered and resolved immediately or, if additional verification is necessary, within ten days, or up to one month with the prosecutor's permission. This period starts from the moment the criminal information is recorded and continues until a decision is made to initiate or refuse to initiate criminal proceedings in the case, or until the materials of the pre-investigation check are sent to the prosecutor.

Furthermore, the reason for sending pre-investigation materials to the prosecutor's office is that reviewing and resolving applications and reports about committed crimes, the legally established procedure for conducting investigations, and monitoring the legality of the issued decision are within the prosecutor's authority.

However, this law does not include a specific provision that considers or restricts the use of digital technologies in the process of registering and resolving criminal complaints, reports, and other information during pre-investigation checks.

Indeed, rules in this area can be found in the criminal procedural legislation of some foreign countries. For example, German criminal procedural legislation provides rules for automatic searching, which essentially regulates the digital verification of statements, reports, and information about crimes[4]. Armenian law requires that a legal entity's report of a crime be in the form of an official letter or in the form of a telegram, telephonogram, radiogram, email, or other verified information[5]. According to the experience of Kyrgyzstan, the pre-trial proceedings stage begins from the registration of statements, reports, and information about a crime or act in the Unified State Register and covers the period up to when the criminal case is brought to trial by the prosecutor. The Unified State Register is an electronic digital database where information about the stages of pre-trial proceedings, performed procedural actions, stages of the criminal case, and participants in the process is entered[6]. At the same time, in the law enforcement practice of countries with digitized criminal proceedings such as Georgia, Kazakhstan, Estonia, and Saudi Arabia, pre-investigation checks are being resolved within a period of up to two days[7].

It should be noted that the existing situation in law enforcement practice required further improvement of this system. That is, until 2019, the reception and registration of reports about crimes and incidents received by internal affairs bodies was carried out mainly through manual paperwork by employees. This situation could cause certain inconveniences in the timely registration of crime-related appeals and their resolution in accordance with the requirements established by law.

As a result of reforms to widely implement information technologies in the activities of internal affairs bodies, this system began to be digitized. Specifically, since 2020, an automated information system for receiving and registering reports of crimes and incidents - the 102 service - has been established. The main advantage of the new system is that every call received by the service is automatically recorded without human intervention. From the moment appeals are registered until they are resolved, they are monitored through the

Ministry of Internal Affairs' situational-analytical center - a single digitalized management platform.

The system's activities are fully monitored through modern video surveillance tools and call centers at the headquarters. Furthermore, due to integration with necessary information systems, it is possible to quickly obtain essential information about incident participants and crime details in real-time, as well as make prompt decisions. According to statistical data, in 2023, the 102 service received nearly 4 million appeals, all of which were considered within the framework of the law. Additionally, the system positively resolved calls that did not require an urgent response or contained clarifying [questions](#)[8].

In general, the rapid registration of crime-related applications, reports, and other information without human intervention is considered a positive process. However, fully digitizing the process of verifying and resolving recorded data in accordance with legal requirements is crucial for increasing operational efficiency. On this basis, starting from 2021, the "E-material" software module was launched, enabling electronic registration of crime-related applications, reports, and other information, as well as maintaining a unified electronic record of the results of their consideration.

According to the module's operating procedure, information about offenses received through the "102 system" is communicated to the official of the pre-investigation inquiry body. The process of resolving the appeal by the employee of the pre-investigation inquiry body is monitored by the situational-analytical center. Additionally, the "E-material" software module enables prosecutorial and departmental oversight of the process of resolving crime-related information.

At the same time, the results of studying pre-trial proceedings practice indicate the need to further strengthen departmental and prosecutorial supervision over the registration of crime-related applications and reports through the "E-material" electronic information system, as well as compliance with procedural legislation when conducting pre-investigation checks on them.

The main reasons for this can be attributed to the failure to conduct comprehensive, complete, and impartial pre-investigation checks in accordance with legal requirements, superficial treatment of appeals, incomplete examination of presented arguments, and a negligent attitude towards official duties.

Naturally, this negative practice leads to the formation of distrust among citizens towards government bodies. Simultaneously, it fosters factors that contribute to corruption crimes among officials authorized to conduct pre-investigation checks.

Based on the aforementioned, the system for recording crimes has been further improved, and a number of new rules have been introduced. This procedure, which relies on the capabilities of the "E-material" electronic information system:

further strengthens internal and external control over the accurate recording of crime-related applications, reports, and other information;

ensures that decisions to refuse the initiation of criminal proceedings are adopted only after thorough examination and unanimous conclusion that there are no signs of a crime in the case;

provides for taking measures to immediately initiate criminal proceedings based on information containing clear signs of a crime.

We believe that as a result of the practical implementation of this procedure:

the system for timely receipt and registration of crime-related applications, reports, and other information will be further improved;

strict adherence to criminal procedural legislation will be achieved when carrying out pre-investigation verification actions;

a foundation will be laid for the prompt consideration of citizens' appeals and the adoption of one of the decisions provided for by law;

prosecutorial and departmental control over pre-investigation activities will be further strengthened, and instances of concealing crimes from accounting will be eliminated;

The process of receiving, registering, and reviewing applications, reports, and other information related to crimes and incidents, as well as conducting pre-investigation checks, will be fully digitized.

Most importantly, factors contributing to corruption crimes related to officials authorized to conduct pre-investigation checks will be eliminated.

This, in turn, will serve to fully mobilize law enforcement agencies to protect human interests, dignity, and rights, as well as to form a corruption-free society and increase the effectiveness of combating corruption.

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